

Article

The Hybrid (Virtual Offsite / Traditional Office) Workplace:
Adapting to Strategic Objectives

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Abstract

In *The Psychology of Management* (1921), Dr. Lillian Gilbreth emphasizes the importance of measurement, synthesis, and analysis in management. In the transition to or from a hybrid (virtual / traditional) workplace, the question is how to objectively measure work. Then, the issue is how, or if, the performance data from a virtual office can be compared to a traditional office. Then, how to relate the measurements of the internal (job and business processes regardless of traditional or virtual location) and external (market) environment. Ultimately, the objective is to remain profitable in an evolving market.

In the transition to or from a hybrid (virtual / traditional) workplace, proactively identifying changes to and adapting the activities of the workforce to align with the strategic objectives of a business is a critical factor in remaining profitable. Whether the workplace is virtual and / or traditional, when changes are not recognized, the organization may miss the opportunity to assess their internal processes and external market environment. Thus, the strategic objectives may no longer align with the market; thereby, impacting productivity and profitability.

Needless to say, establishing performance standards based on organizational objectives, measuring and reporting on actual performance, comparing results with performance and standards, and taking corrective and preventive measures as needed continues to be an evolving science (Van Vliet, 2011; Zeller, 2018 Fall). In addition, "it is of equal importance with the discovery of facts to know what to do with them" (Follett, 1924, p.4). The issue for management is how "to use their 'objective measurements' after they get them; how to insure that they will keep as much of their objectivity as possible; and how to make them operative through, not in spite of, the will of the workmen" (Follett, 1924, p. 20). Furthermore, whether in a traditional or virtual office setting, the workforce is globally situated. Therefore, with an array of value models and cultures impacting global employment relations and practices, making objective measurements operative is a multifaceted venture that requires an understanding of geographic, cultural, and political differences (Zeller, 2016 Fall).

Adding to the challenge is that virtual "workers have more autonomy and responsibility" than their traditional office counterparts; therefore, identifying the variation in job and business processes may be difficult (Zeller, Spring 2018; Cascio, 2000, p. 89). Hence, the performance standards of a hybrid (virtual / traditional) workforce may "defy the possibility of precise measurement" (Follett, 1924, p. 13). For instance, in 1997, Ralph Westfall identified that "reported gains could be biased by the selection of better workers for telework, unreliability of unobserved self-reported productivity gains, inability to separate improvements due to telework from overall management improvements, additional costs for telework not included in analyses, and difficulty in gauging returns that computers gain from telework as more employees participate" (Ruth & Chaudhry, 2008, p. 89; Zeller, 2018 Fall). In 2010, Ware and Grantham noted that "going mobile means changes for the way that work is done and how it is measured and rewarded" (Zeller, 2018 Spring). In essence, the common measurements linking workforce contributions to strategic success must be recognized and agreed upon; then adapted and revised as needed (Zeller, 2016).

Once again, as organizations are planning for the post-pandemic world of work, the objective measurement of productivity in a transitioning hybrid (virtual / traditional) workforce is essential to recognizing where job and business processes may need revisions. The question is how to objectively measure work. Then, the issue is how, or if, the performance data from a virtual office can be compared to a traditional office. Then, how to relate the measurements of the internal (job and business processes regardless of traditional or virtual location) and external (market) environment. The crux of the situation is to gain an ongoing, proactive understanding of the overall impact on profitability.

Discussion

Though hybrid (virtual / traditional) work has recently gained more attention, the option has been available for some time. The following paragraphs offer some insight regarding the experiences of a few organizations with a longstanding hybrid (virtual / traditional) work policy and their plans for the future of their workforce.

IBM

In 2007, IBM had 40% of its 400,000 worldwide employees in virtual offices (Zeller, Summer, 2018; Isidore, 2017). However, with "the rapid increase in Pcs and desktops, the emergence of the Internet, and the adoption of computer networks", the organization's market position, based in "large mainframe computers and centralized data processing systems" , began to decline (Tringalu, 2021). In 2017, "IBM ended its remote work policy" (Staff Writer, 2020). Management determined that the workforce needed to return to traditional offices to improve communication, collaboration, and teamwork. The goal was to regain their market position (Zeller, Summer 2018).

Then, in 2020, as a result of the pandemic, IBM joined many other organizations allowing their employees to work from home. The transition was a return to the virtual office; for others, virtual work was a new experience. Regardless, departments and workers, the business and job processes, and management thereof, were affected. Now, post pandemic, IBM is expecting "about 80% of its employees to work in a hybrid model" (Kaur, 2021).

Honeywell

In 2016, Honeywell's decision to ban its policy offering virtual work office privileges for all employees not in sales or field service was announced "at a time of lackluster growth in the global industrial sector and at a time of restructuring" of the large New Jersey-based organization (Depass, 2016; Zeller, Summer 2018). Basically, Honeywell Executives claimed that "the change was needed 'to encourage the high level of collaboration'" in order to outperform competitors (Depass, 2016; Zeller, Summer 2018).

However, during the pandemic, Honeywell had to reinstate its work from home policy. This time, they had to deal with providing "VPN access to 110 000 employees across 70 countries" (Greig, 2021). Then, in order to "encourage an engaged employee base, the employees were told to turn on their videos" and to keep them on while working (Greig, 2021). Honeywell is evaluating post-pandemic plans for the workforce. Although the organization is reviewing hybrid arrangements, the goal is to get everyone to return to the office (Capgemini, 2021).

Aetna

Aetna's virtual work from home policy, in place for over 20 years, had executive-level support. It was also a formal part of the organization's human resource policies and practices (Fell, 2015; Zeller Fall 2018). Then, in 2016, due to recent trends in the United States healthcare market, Aetna announced a reduction in its workforce as well as revisions to its flexible work-from-home policy. Part of the market trends affecting workforce size is Aetna's withdrawal from 'Obamacare' in some states (HartfordBusiness.com, 2016; Zeller, Fall 2018).

As for during the pandemic, spokesman Ethan Slavin "said the company has 'successfully maintained business continuity' with a partially remote workforce"(Pilon, 2020). For the present, "...all Connecticut-based employees who are currently working from home will continue to do so through the end of the summer" (Pilon, 2020). Moreover, Aetna "will continue to be flexible, methodical, and patient in determining how and when office-based employees are returned to traditional worksites" (Pilon, 2020).

Summary

Dr. Lillian Gilbreth in *The Psychology of Management* (1921) emphasizes the importance of measurement, synthesis, and analysis in management. First, she noted the priority of identifying "the most important unit of measure" (Chapter V, Gilbreth, 1921). Next, she proposes analyzing the unit of measure through division "into its definite cause, parts, or elements, along with an explanation of the principle upon which such a division is made" (Chapter V, Gilbreth, 1921). Then to synthesize, that is to combine the "separate elements of objects of thought into a whole" (Chapter V, Gilbreth, 1921). Ultimately, Dr. Gilbreth acknowledges that "the permanent value and usefulness of the knowledge gained" from analysis is dependent on the scope and depth of the data selected. Then, "the efficiency of the results deduced" from the synthesis of that information is based on what is determined to be included and excluded (Chapter V, Gilbreth, 1921).

Prior to the pandemic, the initial challenges for a hybrid (virtual / traditional) work policy for the organizations in the Discussion section of this article appear to be as a result of changes in the internal and external environments; thereby, creating the need for improved communication and collaboration to improve productivity and to encourage ideas; and revisions to organizational strategies, objectives, and business / job processes. One area of concern is that when each of the organizations required the return to the traditional office, there was a longstanding policy of offering virtual work. That leads to questions, such as, what were the underlying causes of the problems? Were there earlier indications thereof? Another question is whether the requirement to return to the traditional office produced the desired results.

In a post-pandemic world, where organizations are deciding whether to maintain a hybrid or virtual work option or to require all workers to return to traditional offices, there is the opportunity to analyze the roadblocks that led to these earlier decisions to require virtual workers to return to the traditional offices. There is also the opportunity to take into account the challenges and successes with the current pandemic-based transition to virtual work. Ultimately, whether the organization decides on traditional office settings or a hybrid (virtual / traditional) workplace, the overall issue is to objectively identify units of measure to analyze and then synthesize business processes and practices in relation to the strategic objectives in an evolving marketplace.

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